

PREDICTION OF DRIVER'S STRESS AFFECTION IN SIMULATED AUTONOMOUS DRIVING SCENARIOS

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ABSTRACT

We investigate the task of predicting stress affection from physiological data of users experiencing simulations of autonomous driving. We approach this task on two levels of granularity, depending on whether the prediction is performed at the end of the simulation, or along the simulation. In the former, denoted as *coarse-grained* prediction, we employed Decision Trees. In the latter, denoted as *fine-grained* prediction, we employed Echo State Networks, a Recurrent Neural Network that allows efficient learning from temporal data and hence is suitable for pervasive environments. We conduct experiments on a private dataset of physiological data from people participating in multiple driving scenarios simulating different stress-inducing events. The results show that the proposed model is capable of detecting event-related stress reactions, proving the existence of a correlation between stress-inducing events and the physiological data.

Index Terms— Human State Monitoring, Autonomous Driving, Reservoir Computing

1. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous Driving (AD) represents one of the main application contexts of Machine Learning (ML), which provides a wide range of methodologies that aim to provide a safe, efficient, and comfortable autonomous driving system [1]. Commonly, autonomous driving is classified into five levels, denoting an increasing degree of autonomy on the part of the vehicle, up to and including total independence from driver interventions. However, the increasing autonomy from the vehicle must not exclude the human from the driving experience, but rather make their mutual interaction become gradually more *implicit*. In a broader sense, higher-level AD represents

Fig. 1. Representation of Humanistic Intelligence in a simulated autonomous driving scenario.

an instance of Humanistic Intelligence in Cyber-Physical System of Systems: humans and cybernetic components coexist and interact implicitly in a process of mutual empowerment.

Within the TEACHING project [2], we modeled a perspective of this interaction in simulated autonomous driving scenarios (Figure 1) [3, 4, 5], where we define stress as the human reaction due to interaction with critical and unexpected events perceived during the simulation. The user of the driving experience wears devices that detect his or her physiological activity, taken as input from an ML model to predict subjective stress reaction. Then, an agent will adapt the driving style to one that mitigates such reactions. Eventually, the vehicle will learn the driving profiles which maximize the comfort of the user during the driving experience.

In this work, we focus on the first component of the system, and we investigate the task of predicting stress affection from physiological data at two levels of granularity. First, we investigate *coarse-grained* prediction, where we determine

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the overall subjective stress rating of the driver at the end of a simulated driving experience. Then, we investigate *fine-grained* prediction, where we predict event-related stress reaction along the simulation. One fundamental constraint in both tasks is that the model, for being suitable for learning in edge devices, must compromise efficiency in training and effectiveness in inference. Thus, we choose decision trees for the coarse-grained task and, for the fine-grained task, Echo State Networks, which have proven effective in the Human State Monitoring tasks [6]. In our experiments, we employ a private dataset of physiological data from simulated driving experiences, which presents both subjective stress ratings assessed by the user at the end of each simulation, and annotations of stress-inducing events along the simulation.

2. METHODOLOGY

We aim to develop models which can predict the stress reaction of a driver from their physiological data. We consider two main approaches: a coarse-grained approach, where, given a sequence of physiological data, we predict the overall subjective stress rating *at the end* of the driving experience; a fine-grained approach, in which we predict the stress reaction *during* the driving experience. In both approaches, we operate under a constraint dictated by the application context: the deployment of the models in edge environments, in which no assumptions can be made about the computational resources of the devices involved. Consequently, the models must compromise efficiency in training and inference and the quality of their predictions. Formal details of both approaches and the models involved follow.

Coarse-Grained Prediction. In this task, we have a dataset $D = \{(\mathbf{u}_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ where $\mathbf{u}_i = [u(0), u(1), \dots, u(T-1)]$ is the sequence of physiological signals and $y \in \{0, 1\}$ is a ground-truth value for subjective stress rating at the end of the sequence. The objective is to learn the relation between the sequence \mathbf{x}_i and the stress value y_i . To do so, we employed Decision Tree (DT) as learning model. In particular, we trained the DT on the dataset $D' = \{(\mathbf{s}_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, where \mathbf{s}_i is a vector containing mean and standard deviation of each input feature computed on the temporal axis.

Fine-Grained Prediction. Here, we have a dataset $D = \{(\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{y}_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, where \mathbf{u}_i is the sequence of physiological data as in the previous task, while $\mathbf{y} = [y(0), y(1), \dots, y(T-1)]$ is the sequence of ground-truth values for stress reactivity over time. The objective is to learn to detect stress reactions over time. In this task, we employed Echo State Networks (ESNs) [7, 8], which are Reservoir Computing (RC) [9] learning models allowing efficient learning on temporal data by leveraging the evolution of neural activations as a dynamical system. The core component of ESNs is the *reservoir*, a recurrent layer of sparsely connected neurons. Given an input sequence of N_U features and a reservoir with N_R leaky-integrator units [10], we model the state transition function of

the reservoir as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{net}(t) &= \mathbf{W}_{in}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{b}_{rec} + \hat{\mathbf{W}}\mathbf{x}(t-1), \\ \mathbf{x}(t) &= (1-a)\mathbf{x}(t-1) + af(\mathbf{x}_{net}(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_{in} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_U}$ is the input-to-reservoir weight matrix, $\hat{\mathbf{W}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_R}$ is the recurrent reservoir-to-reservoir weight matrix, $\mathbf{b}_{rec} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$ is the reservoir bias term, f is the non-linearity applied to the neurons' cumulative input, $a \in (0, 1]$ is the leaking rate. The hidden state of the reservoir at time $t = 0$ is initialized as $\mathbf{x}(0) = \mathbf{0}$.

The main advantage of using ESNs is that, upon randomized and constrained initialization [7], we keep the matrix $\hat{\mathbf{W}}$ fixed, avoiding backpropagating the error signal through time. Thus, by relying on the higher-dimensional state space spanned by the reservoir, a common way to predict the label at timestep t is to apply a linear transformation to the corresponding state, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{b}_{out}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{b}_{out} define the matrix and the bias term of the transformation respectively. These parameters can be learned efficiently with the closed-form solution of Ridge Regression (RR), i.e.,

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{S}^T(\mathbf{S}\mathbf{S}^T + \lambda\mathbf{I})^{-1}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{Y} denotes the matrix of time-ordered target labels, \mathbf{S} is the matrix of time-ordered reservoir states, λ is an L2-regularization term, and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix.

However, since we cannot always rely on the representation capabilities of randomly initialized reservoirs, there exist techniques that allow improving them in an unsupervised manner. A remarkable example of this category of algorithms is Intrinsic Plasticity (IP) [11, 12], a bio-inspired algorithm based on the *homeostatic plasticity* phenomenon, which improves the information gain of a reservoir by maximizing the entropy of the neural units. This algorithm relies on the extension of the neuron's function with *gain* and *bias* parameters, this algorithm relies on the existence of two additional parameters for each unit in the reservoir, denoted as *gain* and *bias* parameters, for scaling and translating its cumulative input. Formally, given the i -th units, its function is reformulated as $\tilde{f}(x_{net}^i) = f(g^i x_{net}^i + b^i)$. When the non-linearity f is tanh, IP minimizes the Kullback-Leibler divergence between the empirical distribution of the neural units and a desired gaussian $\mathcal{N}_{\mu, \sigma}$, resulting in the following update rule:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta b &= -\eta \left(-\frac{\mu}{\sigma^2} + \frac{\tilde{x}}{\sigma^2} + 1 - \tilde{x}^2 + \mu\tilde{x} \right), \\ \Delta g &= \frac{\eta}{g} + \Delta b x_{net}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of the desired gaussian, \tilde{x} is the result of the application of \tilde{f} in the computation of the state transition, and η is the learning rate.

3. EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT

3.1. Dataset

For this study, we employed a private dataset from a data collection campaign within the TEACHING project. This collection campaign was conducted at the AVL premises (Graz, Austria) with a twofold purpose: (1) having a dataset of physiological data from participants experiencing autonomous driving; (2) evaluating the response of participants to the autonomous driving experience. The dataset is pseudonymized in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and protected by NDA.

Data Collection and Description. The study included 40 participants, 16 women and 24 men, with an average age of 35.5 years ($sd = 8.5$) and an average driving experience of 16.7 years ($sd = 7.8$). Each participant experienced 6 simulations of autonomous driving, each lasting approximately 155 seconds, including conditions such as overtaking during comfort or sport driving, platooning in comfort mode with good or bad weather, and maintaining or changing mode after unexpected braking. Each participant wore two devices during the simulation: a fingertip sensor measuring the Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), and a chest belt for Electrocardiogram (ECG). GSR is a measurement of the electrical conductance of the skin, which reflects the activity of sweat glands in response to psychological and emotional stimuli. ECG records the electrical activity of the heart and can provide important features to classify stress. Both these signals proved to be effective proxies for determining the cognitive state of a human [13]. At the end of each scenario, the participants’ subjective feedback was collected through post-simulation questionnaires, which included questions concerning the stress experienced during the simulation.

The raw dataset obtained after the collection comprised two files with the ECG (26,503,490 samples, sampled at 256 Hz) and GSR and (3,335,389 samples, sampled at 32 Hz) timestamped data, along with the Participant ID and Scenario ID. We produced a third file which, for each timestamp, determines the potentially stressful event experienced by the driver. Finally, we produced an additional file storing the responses from the participants to the post-simulation questionnaires.

Pre-processing. After a round of data cleaning, we obtained a set of 192 sequences (32 participants, 6 scenarios for each participant) of physiological data. Then, we downsampled and synchronized both the signals to 2 Hz, producing sequences with an average length of 300 timesteps.

To cope with the tasks introduced in Section 2, each sequence was labeled with two main approaches. For the coarse-grained task, we equipped each sequence with one binary label y denoting the response of the participant to the question related to the overall stress affection experienced during each scenario, rounded to $\{0, 1\}$. Here, the percentage of positive examples is 55%. For the fine-grained task, we relied on the file annotating potentially stressful events

Fig. 2. GSR signal in presence of stress-inducing events.

and included a sequence of binary labels y where, in each timestep, the value is 1 in the presence of stress-inducing events, 0 otherwise (Figure 2). In this case, the percentage of positive examples is 20%. Note that, while in the first approach, the label comes from the drivers’ subjective measurement of their cognitive stress, in the second the labeling is objective. In the latter, the approach is consistent with the experimental approach in [14], where the labels determine the cognitive state that the participant is *assumed* to experience.

Finally, the dataset underwent an additional pre-processing step depending on the task at hand. In the coarse-grained task, we computed the mean and standard deviations of the input signals over time, reducing each sequence to a vector with 4 features and the corresponding label. In the fine-grained task, each input sequence was normalized by using its statistics computed on the physiological data on the temporal axis.

3.2. Setup

Coherently with the methodology discussed in Section 2, we designed our experiments to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the performance in both the proposed tasks.

First, we split the dataset training, validation and test set depending on the scenario ID. In particular, the training set comprises the scenarios $\{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, the validation set is represented by data in scenario 5, and the test set encloses data from the remaining scenario 6. As a result, each split comprises data from a subset of scenarios from all the participants.

Then, we performed a model selection in both tasks, consisting of a Random Search with 5000 hyperparameter configurations of the model involved, where we selected the best configuration depending on the F1 score achieved on the validation set. In the coarse-grained task, the search space of the DT comprised the following hyperparameters: maximum depth in $\{3, 5, 7, \dots, 21\}$; minimum samples for splitting in $\{2, 3, \dots, 10\}$; minimum samples on leaves in $\{1, 2, \dots, 10\}$; splitting criterion in $\{best, random\}$ based on the entropy.

		Time (in s)	Accuracy (in %)			F1		
			Train	Eval	Test	Train	Eval	Test
CG	DT	$\ll 1$	74.38 ± 2.20	66.25 ± 4.61	59.69 ± 4.28	0.7091 ± 0.0250	0.6033 ± 0.0425	0.5257 ± 0.0531
FG	ESN	16.6 ± 3.8	60.64 ± 4.64	59.60 ± 4.10	60.61 ± 4.52	0.2604 ± 0.0127	0.2638 ± 0.0226	0.2715 ± 0.0191
	IP-ESN	61.5 ± 12.9	88.71 ± 0.13	84.52 ± 0.67	84.05 ± 0.83	0.6583 ± 0.0080	0.5680 ± 0.0037	0.5517 ± 0.0149

Table 1. Results of the experiments performed on the Coarse-Grained (CG) task, and the Fine-Grained (FG) task. We report the mean and standard deviation of the accuracy and F1 score on the training, validation, and test sets. The time column reports the mean and standard deviation of time elapsed for training and testing an instance of the model.

In the fine-grained task, we employed ESNs without and with the adaptation of the reservoir via Intrinsic Plasticity. The search space of the ESN is the following: number of reservoir units in $\{100, 200, \dots, 700\}$; spectral radius of the recurrent matrix in $[0.1, 0.9]$; topology of the recurrent matrix in $\{dense, ring\}$; leaking rate in $\{0.1, 0.2, \dots, 0.9\}$; λ of L2 regularization in $\{1e^{-4}, 1e^{-3}, \dots, 1e^3\}$. For IP, we fixed $\mu = 0$, and selected σ in $[0.1, 0.9]$ and the number of epochs in $\{10, 12, 15\}$. Additionally, in the fine-grained task, we selected the weighting factor of the positive examples (i.e., the timesteps where $y_i(t) = 1$) in $[1, 4]$ and fixed the weight of the negative examples to 1, to cope with the class unbalance.

Finally, we retrained the best configuration 100 times, selected the 10 with the highest F1 on the validation set, and computed the accuracy and F1 score on the test set. Additionally, we report the average time elapsed for training, validation and test.

3.3. Results

In Table 1, we report the performance on both tasks.

On the coarse-grained task, we observe that the performance on the prediction significantly degrades on the test set, approaching almost random guesses. We identify two motivations behind this poor performance: (1) since the labels in this task come from the self-assessment questionnaire, the inter-individual diversity of correlation between physiological data and subjective measurement may lead to poor generalization capabilities; (2) the statistics computed on the input signal do not encode enough information about the significant events, during one simulation, exposed by the physiological activity.

On the fine-grained task, we can observe a more solid performance, and a significant difference between ESNs where the reservoir was left untrained, with the ones where the reservoir was trained via Intrinsic Plasticity. First, we highlight that the IP-ESNs outperform the ESNs with untrained reservoir of at least 25 accuracy points and ~ 0.30 F1 points on all the data splits. Additionally, IP-ESNs are much more stable, and drastically reduce the standard deviation caused by the random initialization of the reservoir. Then, we observed that while the model selection on ESN with untrained reservoir selected a weighting factor of 3.06, with IP-ESNs we selected a value of 1.08, showing that the information gained by the reservoir via IP allows better discrimination even in presence

of data unbalance.

Finally, by comparing the performances on the two tasks, we can observe that the fine-grained approach is more robust than the coarse-grained one. We deduce that local trends of the physiological signals are more representative of the driver’s state in the presence of stress-inducing events. In both tasks, we can observe that all the proposed models attain the efficiency constraint, with timing for training and inference which does not exceed 1 minute.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we investigated the task of predicting a driver’s stress affection from physiological data in autonomous driving simulations. In particular, we investigated coarse-grained prediction, where we predict the overall stress affection after a driving experience, as well as fine-grained prediction, where we predict the stress affection along the driving experience. Since the application context involves edge devices, which may be characterized by low resources, we proposed models which are able to compromise between the efficiency in training with the effectiveness in inference. We performed our studies on a private dataset of temporal data presenting: (1) sequences of measurements of the drivers’ physiological activity during driving simulations; (2) a binary label denoting the overall stress affection after each simulation, used for coarse-grained prediction; (3) a sequence of binary labels denoting stress-inducing events during the simulation, used for fine-grained prediction. To comply with the resource requirements, we employed Decision Trees and Echo State Networks (with untrained and adapted reservoirs) for the two tasks respectively. The results of our experiments lead us to two main conclusions. In fine-grained prediction, IP-ESNs are able to perform a good detection of event-related stress, and assuming a stress condition on the driver in presence of critical events is reasonable. In the coarse-grained prediction, the self-evaluation questionnaire did not represent a solid ground truth for the task, and did not allow us to achieve a good generalization in predicting the overall stress affection.

In the future, we plan to make the work further consistent with the application context and its regulation, by extending it to a federated setting [15]. Then, we aim to explore transfer learning techniques for ESNs to comply with the lack of supervision that may arise in this kind of applications.

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